

Xanthelasma: A Case Report

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Received: May 06, 2025

Accepted: Jun 05, 2025

Published: Jun 11, 2025

Abstract:

Xanthelasma palpebrarum is a prevalent benign dermatological condition characterized by yellowish, cholesterol-rich plaques, predominantly localized to the eyelids. Although asymptomatic in most cases, it often poses cosmetic concerns for affected individuals.

This report discusses a 38-year-old female patient presenting with bilateral, soft, yellowish plaques at the medial canthi of the upper eyelids, progressively enlarging over a two-year period. Surgical excision was performed, and postoperative recovery was uneventful. No recurrence was observed at the 6-month follow-up.

The case emphasizes the clinical relevance of lipid profile evaluation in patients presenting with xanthelasma, as it may serve as an early indicator of underlying dyslipidemia. Additionally, the report highlights the efficacy of surgical excision as a viable treatment option, particularly for patients with cosmetically significant or extensive lesions. Early recognition and appropriate management not only improve cosmetic outcomes but may also contribute to cardiovascular risk assessment and prevention strategies.

Introduction:

The term "xanthelasma" originates from the Greek words *Xanthos*, meaning yellow, and *Elasma*, referring to a thin, beaten metal plate.¹ Xanthelasma palpebrae is the most common type of xanthoma,² presenting as plaque-like, yellow formations on the eyelids, usually near the inner canthus³. They most commonly appear on upper eyelid and less common on lower eyelid¹. These yellowish plaques or papules are localized accumulation of lipid deposits⁴. It is a benign condition which do not cause functional disfigurement but can be cosmetically disturbing to a lot of patients. Patho- physiologically these xanthomas are cholesterol rich deposits which can be seen anywhere in the body during various underlying diseases¹. Various treatment methods for XP include simple surgical excision, cryotherapy, chemical peeling with trichloroacetic acid (TCA), radiofrequency (RF), and destructive techniques or laser therapies such as Nd:YAG, CO₂, and pulsed dye laser treatments^{1,2}.

Hyperlipidaemia, diabetes, and thyroid dysfunction are commonly associated with xanthomas. Abnormal lipid levels are observed in nearly 50% of adults with xanthelasma. These lipid deposits are frequently found in individuals with inherited dyslipidaemias, such as familial hypercholesterolemia and hyperapobetalipoproteinemia. In younger individuals, particularly children, an underlying genetic dyslipidaemia should be considered when xanthelasma is present. Furthermore, primary biliary cholangitis

(PBC) is often marked by xanthelasma, which is strongly linked to severe hypercholesterolemia⁵. Histologically, Lipid-laden histiocytes also called as 'foam cells' are accompanied by endothelial and fibroblastic cell proliferation which are seen accumulating within the superficial dermis, in perivascular and periadnexal areas in Xanthelasma palpebrae³. Xanthelasma palpebrarum has a prevalence of 1.1% in women and 0.3% in men. While it can develop in adults aged 20 to 70, it most commonly occurs between 35 and 55 years. The medial aspect of the upper eyelid is the most frequently affected area, followed by the medial lower eyelid and the lateral canthus. The lesions typically present symmetrically⁵. Other factors, such as familial dyslipidaemia type II and III, have also been shown to have associations with XP.⁶ "Moreover, our analysis revealed a link between xanthelasma palpebrarum and twelve circulating proteins, inferred through genetic prediction. These proteins include FN1, NTM, FCN2, GOLM1, ICAM5, PDE5A, C5, CLEC11A, CXCL1, CCL2, CCL11, and CCL13."⁷

Case Report

This report presents a case of a 38-year-old female patient who visited with the cosmetic complain of yellowish white symptomless patch over the upper eye lid since 3years. After thorough examination patient was explained about the condition. Treatment plan was surgical excision of the patch by conventional method of blade and scalpel.

Following all aseptic conditions and taking all necessary precautions patient was well draped. The area over the face was well painted with betadine. 2% Local anesthesia was administered and the lesion over the upper eye lid was marked using soft tissue marker. With 15 no blade the incision was given over the marked line. Superficial skin along with the underlying fat was excised carefully from over both the eyelids. Interrupted suturing was done and the defect was closed. Betadine dressing was given and patient recalled for follow up.

Figure 1: Preoperative lesion with marking

Figure 2: Incision with 15 no blade

Figure 3: Defect closure and healing after 1 week

Figure 4: Follow up after 3 week

Discussion:

Xanthelasma palpebrarum is the most common type of xanthoma, primarily appearing on the medial portion of the upper eyelid. It may also extend to the surrounding skin, occasionally affecting the lower eyelid or lateral canthus. Mendelson and Masson documented a 40% recurrence rate following the initial excision of xanthelasma palpebrarum (XP), which increased to 60% after a secondary procedure³. This review evaluates the efficacy and complications of various treatments for xanthelasma palpebrarum (XP). Most studies focused on laser and nonsurgical methods, while only 16% examined surgical approaches. Surgical excision had a recurrence rate below 5%, whereas laser treatments achieved >75% lesion clearance in 71% of patients, with recurrence rates between 10% and 31%. Dyspigmentation was the most common side effect, followed by scarring. Surgery remains the standard and conventional and cost-efficient method for deeper Xanthelasma Palpebrarum lesions. Small lesions can be excised safely with minimal scarring, but larger ones carry risks of eyelid retraction, ectropion, and pigmentation changes, often requiring reconstruction. Recent studies highlight blepharoplasty with grafts or flaps. While surgical techniques had a low overall complication and recurrence rate (0.5%), they remain invasive, with potential postoperative risks, including scarring and eyelid deformities⁵.

Conclusion:

Xanthelasma palpebrarum a benign condition with lipid filled deposit. There are various treatment modalities for Xanthelasma and in this case the conventional surgical excision method is considered. The results of follow up are satisfying to patient. Surgical excision remains a reliable and effective treatment for xanthelasma palpebrarum, particularly in cases of extensive or recurrent lesions. The procedure allows for complete removal, with minimal recurrence when combined with appropriate lipid management. Proper wound care and follow-up are essential to ensure optimal healing and aesthetic outcomes. While alternative treatments exist, surgical excision provides immediate results and is a preferred option for well-selected patients.

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